

A Study of Various Types of Cyber Crimes in India with Their Specified Classification

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Abstract

Cybercrime primarily refers to actions that use computers and the internet as a means of directly or indirectly obtaining a person's private information and publishing it online without that person's knowledge or permission, with the intention of damaging that person's reputation or causing them physical or psychological harm. As technology has advanced, there has been a noticeable rise in the number of cybercrimes. As reliance on the internet has grown, so too have the number of crimes against women. This is mostly due to the fact that over half of internet users lack sufficient training and education, are unaware of how online platforms operate, and are uninformed about technological improvements. As a result, protecting women and children who are harassed and mistreated for voyeuristic pleasures has become extremely difficult for law enforcement organizations around the world due to cybercrime. Women are frequently the target of impersonation, cyber stalking, and cyber pornography. India is one of the few nations that have passed the IT Act 2000 to address cybercrimes and protect women from being exploited by predatory men. However, this act does not address some of the most serious threats to women's security, and problems involving women continue to escalate.

Keywords : Cybercrimes, Information Technology Act, 2000, Online Platforms, Face book, Pornography, WhatsApp.

1.1 INTRODUCTION:-

The emergence of technology has allowed women to discover their strengths and expand their abilities. As the society is progressing, the internet holds an important place in our everyday's lives and it is one of the most important and useful communication tools. Nevertheless, along with the growing reliance on cyberspace, online crimes targeting women have also surged. For many years, women worldwide have been subjected to various forms of harassment. With the rise of technology and digitalization, individuals can connect virtually with anyone, at any time, and from anywhere around the world. This modernization has led to the rise of cybercrime. For voyeuristic enjoyment, women are frequently targeted for abuse and harassment on internet platforms. One of the primary factors contributing to this is that over half of online users are not completely familiar with the way online platforms like Face book, Skype, WhatsApp, etc. work. Users receive very little instruction and training that is sufficient. Furthermore, such horrible acts have been made possible by a lack of knowledge about technological progress. Cyber stalking, cyber pornography, impersonation, and other forms of cyber harassment are frequently directed at women. As a result of the victim's confidence in the perpetrator, they frequently disclose their personal information or data, leading to daily cybercrimes. The idea of cybercrime has changed, and now the victims are mostly women who have been tricked by technology. Several nations where the main priority has always been the safety of women have seen a significant surge in the frequency of cybercrimes. In an effort to safeguard women from exploitation by ruthless criminals and provide them with the support they need to combat all transgressions, India is one of the few nations that have passed the IT Act 2000 to address cybercrime-related concerns. Although many organizations have addressed the problems associated with cybercrime in an effort to increase public knowledge of women's

safety, there has still been a significant rise in this area, which has a detrimental effect on the nation's progress.

Cybercrime can be described as "any unlawful act in which a computer is a tool, an objective, or both." The usage of computers has become quite widespread and popular lately. Nonetheless, cybercrime has resulted both domestically and globally from the abuse of technology in cyberspace. The Indian parliament passed the law on technological information in 2000 with the goal of controlling criminal behaviour in cyberspace and safeguarding the technological progress system. India's first international legislation covered technology in the domains of e-commerce, e-governance, and electronic banking services, as well as sanctions and penalties for computer offenses. The prevalent forms of cybercrime and methods for its prevention will be covered in this article.

1.2 DEFINITION OF CYBER CRIMES:-

"Cybercrimes are generally defined as "crimes committed against individuals or groups of individuals with a criminal motive to intentionally harm the victim's reputation or cause physical or mental harm, or loss, to the victim directly or indirectly, using modern telecommunication networks such as the Internet (networks including chat rooms, emails, notice boards, and groups) and mobile phones ".¹

The use of computers and the internet are included in cybercrime. By releasing or posting a person's private or sensitive data online with the intent of harming their reputation and causing them physical or psychological harm, either directly or indirectly, it holds their privacy at risk. Since women are often inexperienced and unfamiliar with the digital world, they are more susceptible to the allure of technology, making them the targets of these criminals.

"Cybercrime against women" is defined by Debarati Halder and K. Jaishankar as "crimes targeted against women with a motive to intentionally harm the victim psychologically and physically, using modern telecommunication networks such as internet and mobile phones" from a gender perspective.

Cybercrime can be committed by using technology, when the gadget is both the target of the crime and a tool for conducting it. Malware that targets victims in order to hack them and destroy or corrupt their data for financial gain is one example. Data theft and fraud made possible by cyberspace are examples of other types of cybercrime.

1.3 UNDERSTANDING THE CYBER CRIMES:-

The word "cybercrime" encompasses any offense that makes use of a computer or a network. When the computer is a weapon, a target, or both, it is an illegal offense. It refers to crimes perpetrated using electronic communication channels. It's stealing a little bit of the computer through the internet. Crime is increasing rapidly here. Using the Internet, cyber thieves are engaging in a wide range of illegal actions. In the past, cybercrime was mostly carried out by individuals or small gangs, but nowadays, cybercriminals belong to a wide range of groups and categories, including professional hackers, organized hackers, scammers, phishers, insiders, malware writers, spammers, children and teenagers between the ages of 6 and 18, and more.

The newest and possibly most complex issue in the cyber world is cybercrime. Cybercrime can be defined as those species of which the genus is the conventional crime and where either the computer is an object or subject of the conduct constituting crime.²Cybercrime

¹ Debrati Halder & K. Jaishankar, Cyber Crimes Against Women in India

² Ashish Pandey - Cyber Crime Detection & Prevention (1st Edn.) 2006 JBA Publisher.

encompasses any criminal conduct that uses a computer as a target for instrumentality or as a tool to commit more crimes.³

"Unlawful conduct when the computer is either a tool or a target, or both" might be a broad definition of cybercrime.⁴

1.4 CATEGORIES OF CYBER CRIMES:-

When we study about cyber crimes then the same could be classified into three main categories on the basis of nature and they are as follows:-

- > When computer is used as the target.
- > When computer is used as the source to aid the commission of the crime.
- > When computer is related to the crime incidentally.

A.) WHEN COMPUTER ITSELF IS USED AS THE TARGET :-

- Vandalization of computer system or computer networks
- Vandalization of operating systems and programs
- Data theft or misuse of the information
- Blackmail of the persons by misusing of the personal browsing history

B.) WHEN COMPUTER IS USED AS THE SOURCE TO AID THE COMMISSION OF CRIME:-

Due to rise of the usage of the minicomputer systems, there is the instant growth of the traditional cyber crimes like software piracy, counterfeiting, and copyright violation of computer programs and one of the best examples where computer was used as source for the commission of crime is terrorist attack done on the Indian Parliament on 13th of December 2001.⁵

C.) WHEN COMPUTER IS RELATED TO THE CRIME INCIDENTALLY:-

This category includes crimes when a computer is not necessary for the crime to occur, but computerization does contribute to the crime by processing vast amounts of data and making it more challenging to identify and trace the crime. The best examples of this type of crime are illegal banking transactions and money laundering. In one instance, a suspect changed a patient's prescription and dose on a hospital computer, so committing murder.⁶

1.5 TRADITIONAL CLASSIFICATION OF CYBER CRIMES:-

Cyber Crimes can be classified on the traditional basis as it was suggested by Ulrich Sieber⁷ and it includes basically two groups which are as follows :-

- 1.) Cyber Crimes of economic category.
- 2.) Cyber Crimes against the violation of privacy.

We will study these two heads of cyber crimes one by one:-

A.) CYBER CRIMES OF ECONOMIC CATEGORY:-

In this type of cyber crimes, basically criminals target both the hardware and software of the computer system which includes the theft of the computer data through the illegal means, sabotage of the computer system and basically it involves the using of the computer without authority for the illegal purpose. It also involves the illegal usage of the software and computer database to extract the information for the purpose of criminal activities.

B.) CYBER CRIMES AGAINST THE VIOLATION OF PRIVACY:-

³ Duggal Pawan

⁴ Nagpal R. -What is Cybercrime?

⁵ Similar use of computer technology was made by the terrorist who attacked the world Trade centre in U.S.A. on September 11, 2001 leading to its collapse and causing mass destruction of property and human life

⁶ Suri R.K. and Chhabra T.N. : Cyber Crime (2003) Reprint P. 49

⁷ Ulrich Sieber: The International Hand book on computer crime, p. 38.

In cases of cyber crimes that involve a breach of the right to privacy, the computer system primarily serves as a means to commit the offense. In reality, many of the actions categorized as cyber crimes of an economic nature also fall into this category. However, the key distinction is that these acts do not violate the victim's property rights but rather infringe upon their legal rights, particularly the right to privacy.

Typically, privacy refers to an individual's right to remain undisturbed. However, in the context of online activities, it implies anonymity — meaning a person's identity and personal information should remain undisclosed. For instance, when someone shares their details with a bank, retailer, medical professional, or lawyer, they expect that this information will be used only for its intended purpose and not shared with others unless the individual has clearly or implicitly agreed to it.

However, there are situations where unethical individuals disclose confidential or personal information obtained from clients for malicious purposes that go beyond the original intent for which the information was shared. Likewise, when someone sends an email, they trust that it will be accessed only by the intended recipient. Unfortunately, this expectation of privacy is often not upheld and can be exploited for criminal activities. Similarly, when sensitive and confidential data is stored on a computer, it is essential to protect its secrecy and integrity as part of the user's right to privacy, to ensure it is not misused by cyber criminals.⁸

1.6 GENERAL CLASSIFICATION OF CYBER CRIMES:-

General classification comprises of the four categories:-

- Cybercrimes against individuals
- Cybercrimes against property
- Cybercrimes against organisations
- Cybercrimes against society

These types of cybercrimes include lots of criminal activities and we will discuss them one by one:-

CYBERCRIMES AGAINST INDIVIDUALS

a.) Email spoofing

When a cybercriminal forges the sender's email address to make a message look as though it came from a trustworthy source, this is known as email spoofing. People are tricked by spoof emails, which frequently cause them to click on harmful links or divulge personal information, which can lead to identity theft or financial loss.

b.) Spamming

Sending unsolicited emails or communications to a large number of recipients is known as spamming. While some spam emails are harmless, others are used to promote scams, spread malware, or carry out phishing attacks, endangering the privacy of those who receive them.

c.) Cyber Defamation

The act of damaging someone's reputation by making untrue claims online is known as cyber defamation. This can occur through emails, websites, or posts on social media where someone's reputation is harmed by the publication of defamatory content, which frequently has major repercussions for the victim.

d.) Cyber stalking

The act of frightening or harassing someone online is known as cyberstalking. Cyberstalkers might follow a person's online activities, send unsolicited communications, or make their victim feel insecure or afraid.

⁸ Supra fn. 17. at. p.28

e.) Phishing

Phishing attacks entail tricking people into divulging private information, including login passwords or bank account information, usually through phony emails or websites that look authentic. One of the most popular techniques still employed by cybercriminals to obtain private data is phishing.

CYBERCRIMES AGAINST PROPERTY

a.) Credit card Fraud

When a cybercriminal obtains unauthorized access to a person's credit card information, credit card fraud happens, resulting in unlawful purchases and monetary loss. This crime is frequently perpetrated through card skimming, data breaches, or phishing.

b.) Intellectual Property Theft

Unauthorized use or dissemination of trade secrets, patents, and copyrighted content are examples of intellectual property crimes. Software piracy, copyright violations, and trademark infringement are a few examples. These crimes hurt companies and artists by denying them the money they deserve or by harming their reputation.

c.) Internet Time Theft

When someone uses another person's internet connection without authorization, it's known as internet time theft. Businesses are frequently impacted by this crime since employees may abuse company resources for personal purposes, resulting in needless expenses for the organization.

d.) Cyber Vandalism

The act of damaging or defacing someone's online property, like changing a person's website or social media profile, is known as cyber vandalism. This can cause trouble and damage to one's reputation by erasing data, corrupting files, or publishing objectionable content.

CYBERCRIMES AGAINST ORGANISATIONS

a.) Unauthorised access and data theft

Unauthorized access is entering a company's computer systems without authorization, frequently with the intention of obtaining confidential information. This can contain financial data, corporate secrets, or personal information; stolen data is either sold or utilized as a form of blackmail.

b.) Denial of Service Attacks

A DoS attack is an effort to stop legitimate users from using a company's services by flooding its servers with too much bogus traffic. Operations are disrupted by DoS attacks, which may result in lost revenue and harm to one's reputation.

c.) Virus and Malware Attacks

Malicious programs called viruses and malware are loaded on a system with the intent to harm it, steal data, or interfere with normal operations. Businesses are regularly affected by ransom ware attacks, in which attackers encrypt files and demand payment to unlock them.

d.) Web Jacking

A form of cybercrime known as "web jacking" occurs when an attacker takes over a company's website and frequently reroutes it to a malicious one. Data breaches, malware distribution, or extortion demands may result from this. Because it deceives website visitors and damages a company's reputation, web jacking is particularly problematic in the context of cyber security.

CYBERCRIMES AGAINST SOCIETY:-

a.) Forgery

Computer-based forgery entails producing fictitious documents, such as official forms, certificates, or currency. Cybercriminals who have access to top-notch printers and scanners can create fake papers, seriously harming businesses' finances and reputations.

b.) Cyber terrorism

Cyber terrorism is the use of technology to threaten or damage individuals, groups, or governments. With the intention of causing panic and upsetting social order, cyber terrorists may distribute propaganda, hack government databases, or conduct cyber attacks on vital infrastructure.

1.6 CONCLUSION:-

As society is progressing, usage of the cyber space have been increased and after covid , usage of the online medium have become common for everyone and everyone is totally dependent on the online sources . We can say that using online platforms is boon for the society at large but on the other hand we can say that it's curse also as now we are dealing with lots of cyber crimes and in this paper there is the classification of the cyber crimes and various aspects of the cyber crimes have been discussed in this paper whether it's general classification or traditional classification because it's necessary for all to have the knowledge regarding cyber crimes.

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9. *Technology-mediated violence against women in India*, IT FOR CHANGE, (Jan 29, 2021), <https://itforchange.net/e-vaw/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/DISCUSSIONPAPER.pdf>
10. "Information privacy, or data privacy (or data protection), concerns personally identifiable information or other sensitive information and how it is collected, stored, used, and finally destroyed or deleted – in digital form or otherwise. In relation to technology, it pertains to the relationship between collection and dissemination of data, technology, the public expectation of privacy, and the legal and political issues surrounding them."

